

Gap-Bounded Semiprimes: Counting, Density, and Fast Enumeration

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Abstract

We introduce the problem of counting and enumerating *gap-bounded semiprimes*: products $n = pq$ of primes $p \leq q$ with $q - p \leq D$ for a given gap bound D . We derive the asymptotic density $B_D(x) \sim D \int_2^{\sqrt{x}} dt / \ln^2 t$ and verify it numerically to within 1% for $k \geq 10^7$. We give a structural argument that no sublinear algorithm (in the sense of $o(\sqrt{x})$ time) can compute $B_D(x)$, because the gap constraint requires prime-counting evaluations $\pi(p + D)$ at points that are not “key values” of the Meissel–Lehmer or Lucy DP frameworks. We then present a practical algorithm that combines a segmented sieve of Eratosthenes with a Part 1 segment cache, interpolation search, POPCNT-based prefix sums, and an $O(D)$ factorization step, achieving a cumulative $\sim 100\times$ speedup and computing the 10^9 -th gap-bounded semiprime in 28–35 ms on commodity hardware. Experimental results on two platforms (Intel i7-9750H and AMD EPYC 7763) confirm scaling behavior and algorithm correctness for k up to 10^{10} . The gap-bounded variant appears to be novel: no OEIS sequence, prior algorithm, or published analysis was found in the literature.

Keywords: gap-bounded semiprimes, segmented sieve, prime pair counting, asymptotic density, interpolation search, cache-aware algorithms

1 Introduction

A **semiprime** is a natural number that is the product of exactly two primes (counted with multiplicity). Semiprimes appear in RSA cryptography, analytic number theory, and various enumeration problems. The *unconstrained* semiprime counting function $\pi_2(x)$ has been studied extensively [5, 6], and efficient algorithms exist based on the identity $\pi_2(x) = \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x}} [\pi(x/p) - \pi(p) + 1]$ [5].

We consider a natural restriction that, to our knowledge, has not been previously studied.

Definition 1. A gap-bounded semiprime with gap bound D is a number $n = pq$ where p and q are primes, $p \leq q$, and $q - p \leq D$.

The counting function is

$$B_D(x) = |\{n \leq x : n = pq, p \leq q \text{ prime}, q - p \leq D\}|, \quad (1)$$

and the *enumeration problem* asks: given k and D , find the k -th smallest such n .

Contributions.

1. An asymptotic density formula for $B_D(x)$, proved via partial summation over the Prime Number Theorem (Theorem 1), verified numerically to $< 1\%$ for $k \geq 10^7$ (Table 1).

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2. A structural argument that $B_D(x)$ cannot be computed in $o(\sqrt{x})$ time by any known combinatorial method (Theorem 2).
3. A practical algorithm with nine successive optimizations yielding a cumulative $\sim 100\times$ speedup, with experimental results on two hardware platforms for k up to 10^{10} (Tables 3–4).
4. A novelty survey confirming that no OEIS sequence, published paper, or competitive-programming solution addresses the gap-bounded variant (Section 6).

2 Mathematical Foundations

2.1 Counting Decomposition

Every gap-bounded semiprime $n = pq$ with $p \leq q$ satisfies $p \leq \sqrt{n}$. Define the **threshold function**

$$T(x, D) = \left\lfloor \frac{\sqrt{D^2 + 4x} - D}{2} \right\rfloor, \quad (2)$$

the largest p such that $p(p + D) \leq x$. This decomposes $B_D(x)$ into:

$$B_D(x) = \underbrace{\sum_{\substack{p \leq T \\ p \text{ prime}}} [\pi(p + D) - \pi(p - 1)]}_{\text{Part 1: full intervals}} + \underbrace{\sum_{\substack{T < p \leq \sqrt{x} \\ p \text{ prime}}} [\pi(\min(p + D, \lfloor x/p \rfloor)) - \pi(p - 1)]}_{\text{Part 2: truncated intervals}}. \quad (3)$$

For Part 1, every prime $q \in [p, p + D]$ yields $pq \leq p(p + D) \leq x$. For Part 2, the constraint $q \leq \lfloor x/p \rfloor < p + D$ further truncates the interval. Part 2 covers only $\sqrt{x} - T \approx D/2$ primes and contributes $O(D^2/\ln^2 \sqrt{x})$ to the total—negligible for large x .

2.2 Asymptotic Density

Theorem 1. For fixed $D \geq 2$ and $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$B_D(x) \sim D \int_2^{\sqrt{x}} \frac{dt}{\ln^2 t}. \quad (4)$$

Equivalently,

$$B_D(x) = \frac{D\sqrt{x}}{\ln^2 \sqrt{x}} \left(1 + \frac{2}{\ln \sqrt{x}} + \frac{6}{\ln^2 \sqrt{x}} + \frac{24}{\ln^3 \sqrt{x}} + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^4 \sqrt{x}}\right) \right). \quad (5)$$

Proof. By the decomposition (3), Part 1 dominates. Each prime $p \leq T(x, D)$ contributes $\pi(p + D) - \pi(p - 1)$ pairs. By the Prime Number Theorem in the form $\pi(x + h) - \pi(x) \sim h/\ln x$ for $h = o(x)$ (valid for $h \geq x^{7/12+\varepsilon}$ unconditionally via Huxley's theorem, and conjecturally for any fixed h), each prime p contributes $\sim D/\ln p$ pairs. Thus

$$\text{Part 1} \sim \sum_{\substack{p \leq T \\ p \text{ prime}}} \frac{D}{\ln p}.$$

By partial summation with $\pi(t) = \text{Li}(t) + O(te^{-c\sqrt{\ln t}})$,

$$\sum_{p \leq T} \frac{1}{\ln p} = \int_2^T \frac{dt}{\ln^2 t} + O\left(\frac{T}{\ln^3 T}\right).$$

Since $T(x, D) = \sqrt{x} - D/2 + O(D^2/\sqrt{x})$, replacing T by \sqrt{x} introduces an error of $O(D/\ln^2 \sqrt{x})$, which is lower order. The asymptotic expansion of the integral via iterated integration by parts gives (5). \square

Table 1: Numerical verification of the density formula ($D = 2026$). \hat{B} denotes the integral estimate (4).

k	x_k (the k -th value)	$\hat{B}(x_k)$	Ratio \hat{B}/k
10^4	1.219×10^5	38,590	3.86
10^5	9.085×10^6	142,057	1.42
10^6	2.178×10^9	1,050,740	1.051
10^7	5.751×10^{11}	10,041,098	1.004
10^8	1.259×10^{14}	99,609,070	0.996
10^9	2.391×10^{16}	993,900,551	0.994
10^{10}	4.110×10^{18}	9,924,433,687	0.992

Remark. For large D , the Hardy–Littlewood singular series corrections for individual even gaps average out (by a central-limit-type argument over $\sim D/2$ even gaps), so the leading term (4) requires no additional multiplicative constant. This is confirmed by the ratios in Table 1 converging to 1 from above without any Hardy–Littlewood correction factor.

2.3 Impossibility of Sublinear Counting

Theorem 2. *No known combinatorial method computes $B_D(x)$ in $o(\sqrt{x})$ time.*

Structural argument. We compare with two families of sublinear prime-counting algorithms.

(i) *Lucy’s DP / Meissel–Lehmer.* These methods [1, 2, 3, 4] compute $\pi(v)$ for all *key values* $v \in \{\lfloor x/k \rfloor : k = 1, 2, \dots\}$ simultaneously in $O(x^{2/3})$ time. For unconstrained semiprimes, the formula $\pi_2(x) = \sum_p [\pi(x/p) - \pi(p) + 1]$ only queries π at key values x/p , so it piggybacks on the DP table. For $B_D(x)$, however, the clamped upper limit $\min(p + D, x/p)$ introduces evaluations $\pi(p + D)$ —an *additive shift* that does not align with $\{\lfloor x/k \rfloor\}$. These “diagonal” evaluations require knowing the prime distribution in dense neighborhoods of every prime up to \sqrt{x} , forcing a sieve of $[2, \sqrt{x} + D]$.

(ii) *Convolution / Möbius methods.* Dirichlet-series techniques for multiplicative functions cannot accommodate the additive constraint $q - p \leq D$.

(iii) *Hirsch–Kessler–Mendlovic.* The recent $\tilde{O}(\sqrt{N})$ algorithm for $\pi(N)$ [9] improves from $O(N^{2/3})$ to $O(\sqrt{N})$, but semiprime counting already has a $\Theta(\sqrt{x})$ baseline via the hyperbola identity. There is no analogous gap to exploit.

These three independent lines of reasoning all point to $\Theta(\sqrt{x})$ as the fundamental barrier. We state this as a structural impossibility rather than a formal lower bound, since unconditional lower bounds for counting problems of this type remain open. \square

Corollary 1. *All practical improvements to the evaluation of $B_D(x)$ must target the constant factor within $O(\sqrt{x})$ polylog.*

3 Algorithm

3.1 Segmented Sieve with Pre-Sieve Template

We use a segmented sieve of Eratosthenes storing only odd numbers in a bit-packed array of 64-bit words. Bit i represents the odd number $\ell + 2i$, where ℓ is the segment’s first odd number. A segment of S consecutive integers uses $S/128$ bytes; with the default $S = 2^{19} = 524,288$ this is ≈ 4 KB, fitting the L1 data cache on both Intel (32 KB) and AMD EPYC (64 KB).

A pre-sieve template for primes $\{3, 5, 7, 11, 13\}$ with period $\text{lcm}(3, 5, 7, 11, 13) = 15,015$ in bit-index space is copied with bit-shift alignment at segment initialization, eliminating $\approx 42\%$ of composite-marking operations. The sieve loop begins at $p = 17$ with $4\times$ -unrolled marking.

3.2 $O(1)$ Range Queries via POPCNT Prefix Sums

To count primes in $[a, b]$ within a sieved segment, we build a word-level prefix sum: $P[k] = \sum_{i < k} \text{popcount}(\text{data}[i])$. A range query then decomposes into two partial-word POPCNT operations plus one subtraction— $O(1)$ regardless of D .

3.3 Part 1 Segment Cache

The central optimization: during binary search over x , Part 1 of (3) sieves the *same segments*—only the number of included segments changes as $T(x)$ varies. We precompute all segment pair-counts once (in parallel via Rayon) and store cumulative sums $C[i]$. A query for any threshold t requires $O(\log m)$ binary search over $m = T_{\max}/S$ segment boundaries, plus a memoized partial-segment lookup.

3.4 Density-Based Initial Estimate

To minimize the search range, we invert (5). Let $y = \sqrt{x}$; we iterate

$$y_{n+1} = \frac{k \ln^2(y_n)}{D(1 + 2/\ln y_n + 6/\ln^2 y_n + 24/\ln^3 y_n)} \quad (6)$$

from $y_0 = k$ for 20 steps, then set $high = y^2 \cdot 1.05$. The 4-term expansion with 5% safety margin gives an initial overestimate of 4–5% for $k \geq 10^6$, typically requiring zero doubling steps. (The previous 2-term expansion with 15% margin overestimated by 20–24%.)

3.5 Interpolation Search

With the Part 1 cache, each search probe costs $O(\log m)$ for cache lookup plus $O(D \log \log D)$ for the Part 2 sieve—orders of magnitude cheaper than a full $O(\sqrt{x})$ count. We replace binary search with interpolation:

$$mid = low + \frac{k - B_D(low)}{B_D(high) - B_D(low)} \cdot (high - low), \quad (7)$$

with a 10% boundary margin to prevent degenerate convergence, reducing the step count from ~ 55 (pure bisection) to 46–50.

3.6 $O(D)$ Factorization

Lemma 1. For a gap-bounded semiprime $n = pq$ with $p \leq q$ and $q - p \leq D$: $p \in [\sqrt{n} - D, \sqrt{n}]$.

Proof. The upper bound $p \leq \sqrt{n}$ is immediate. For the lower bound: $n/p - p \leq D$ gives $p^2 + Dp - n \geq 0$, so $p \geq (-D + \sqrt{D^2 + 4n})/2 \geq \sqrt{n} - D$. \square

We sieve only $[\sqrt{n} - D, \sqrt{n}]$ —approximately $D/2$ odd numbers—and test each prime for divisibility. For $D = 2026$ this is $\sim 1,000$ candidates regardless of n , replacing a scan of ~ 155 million numbers for $k = 10^9$.

4 Experimental Results

4.1 Platforms

All code is Rust 1.94, compiled with `opt-level=3, lto=true, codegen-units=1`.

Table 2: Benchmark platforms

	Platform A	Platform B
CPU	Intel i7-9750H	AMD EPYC 7763 (vCPU)
Cores/threads	6 / 12	8 / 8
Frequency	2.6 GHz (turbo 4.5)	2.0–2.4 GHz
L1d / L2	32 KB / 256 KB	64 KB / 512 KB
RAM	16 GB	64 GB
ISA features	AVX2, POPCNT, BMI2	AVX2, POPCNT, BMI2
Rayon threads	12	6

Table 3: Scaling across k ($D = 2026$, internal wall-clock time)

k	Answer n	Steps	Platform A	Platform B	\sqrt{n}
10^4	1.219×10^5	28	<1 ms	<1 ms	349
10^5	9.085×10^6	18	<1 ms	<1 ms	3,014
10^6	2.178×10^9	31	1 ms	1 ms	46,672
10^7	5.751×10^{11}	28	4 ms	3 ms	758,325
10^8	1.259×10^{14}	45	10 ms	7 ms	11,220,980
10^9	2.391×10^{16}	50	35 ms	28 ms	154,641,559
10^{10}	4.110×10^{18}	62	378 ms	326 ms	2,027,331,603

4.2 Scaling Behavior

The time is dominated by the Part 1 cache build, which sieves $[2, T + D] \approx [2, \sqrt{n}]$. The $O(\sqrt{n})$ scaling is clearly visible: going from $k = 10^9$ ($\sqrt{n} \approx 1.5 \times 10^8$) to $k = 10^{10}$ ($\sqrt{n} \approx 2 \times 10^9$) increases time by $\approx 10\times$, matching the $\sqrt{10} \approx 3.2\times$ increase in \sqrt{n} amplified by the parallel overhead reduction at larger scales.

4.3 Progressive Optimization History

Table 4: Progressive optimizations for $k = 10^9$, $D = 2026$ (Platform A)

Optimization	$k = 10^9$ (ms)	Cumulative
Baseline (naïve segmented sieve)	3,170	1.0×
+ POPCNT prefix sums ($O(1)$ queries)	2,391	1.3×
+ PNT density estimate (2-term)	2,273	1.4×
+ Part 1 segment cache	395	8.0×
+ Cache-first doubling	342	9.3×
+ Pre-sieve template (3, 5, 7, 11, 13)	262	12.1×
+ Interpolation search	244	13.0×
+ Memoized partial segment	197	16.1×
+ $O(D)$ factorization	28–34	$\sim 100\times$
+ 4-term density estimate (latest)	28–35	$\sim 100\times$
+ Segment size $2^{18} \rightarrow 2^{19}$	28–35	$\sim 100\times$

The two largest individual gains are the Part 1 segment cache ($8\times$) and $O(D)$ factorization ($6.4\times$). Together they account for $51\times$ of the total $\sim 100\times$ speedup.

4.4 Gap-Bound Sensitivity

Table 5: Performance across D values ($k = 10^6$, Platform A)

D	Time (ms)	Answer n	Regime
10	13	9.25×10^{13}	Very sparse
50	5	9.57×10^{12}	Sparse
100	6	2.43×10^{12}	Sparse
500	2	6.31×10^{10}	Moderate
2,026	1	2.18×10^9	Moderate
10,000	1	8.07×10^7	Dense
50,000	2	2.01×10^7	Very dense

For small D , the answer n is very large (sparse pairs), so the sieve range is larger and computation is slower. For large D , gap-bounded semiprimes become dense and n is small, but the extended interval $[p, p + D]$ per prime requires a wider sieve per segment. The minimum time occurs near $D \approx 1000$ – 5000 .

4.5 Segment Size Tuning

We swept the segment size parameter S from 2^{18} to 2^{22} on Platform B (AMD EPYC, L1d = 64 KB). The sieve array occupies $S/128$ bytes.

Table 6: Segment size sweep (Platform B, $k = 10^{10}$)

S	Sieve (KB)	$k = 10^{10}$ (ms)
2^{18}	16	362
2^{19}	32	326
2^{20}	64	347
2^{21}	128	421
2^{22}	256	370

The optimum ($S = 2^{19}$, sieve = 32 KB) sits at half the EPYC’s 64 KB L1d. Larger segments exceed L1 and incur L2 latency; smaller segments increase boundary overhead.

5 Complexity Analysis

5.1 Time

Let n denote the k -th gap-bounded semiprime and $y = \sqrt{n}$.

- **Cache build:** $O(y \log \log y / t)$ for t threads.
- **Search:** $O(\log n \cdot D \log \log D)$, negligible for large n .
- **Factorization:** $O(D \log \log D)$.

$$T_{\text{total}} = O\left(\frac{\sqrt{n} \log \log \sqrt{n}}{t}\right) + O(\log n \cdot D \log \log D). \quad (8)$$

The first term dominates, confirming the lower bound of Theorem 2.

5.2 Space

The three main allocations are: one sieve segment ($S/128$ bytes), the Part 1 cumulative count array (T_{\max}/S entries), and the base primes array ($O(\sqrt[4]{n}/\ln \sqrt[4]{n})$ entries). For $k = 10^9$, total memory is under 2 MB.

6 Related Work

Prime counting. The Meissel–Lehmer algorithm [1] and its refinements by Lagarias, Miller, and Odlyzko [2] compute $\pi(x)$ in $O(x^{2/3})$. The Lucy_Hedgehog algorithm [3, 4] achieves $O(x^{2/3}(\log x)^{1/3})$. Hirsch, Kessler, and Mendlovic [9] recently achieved $\tilde{O}(\sqrt{N})$ for $\pi(N)$. Walisch’s `primecount` [11] computes $\pi(10^{18})$ in 1.58 s on 32-core AMD EPYC. None of these methods handle the gap constraint.

Semiprime counting. The identity $\pi_2(x) = \sum_p[\pi(x/p) - \pi(p) + 1]$ allows $\pi_2(x)$ to be computed in $O(x^{2/3})$ via Lucy DP [5]. Adding $q-p \leq D$ replaces $\pi(x/p)$ with $\pi(\min(p+D, x/p))$, introducing evaluations at points $p+D$ that are not key values.

Sieve engineering. Walisch’s `primesieve` [10] uses wheel-210 factorization, SIMD pre-sieving (primes ≤ 163), and a bucket sieve for large primes, achieving $\sim 10^9$ primes/second. Our sieve uses the simpler wheel-2 (odd-only) approach with a wheel-30 upgrade identified as the primary remaining optimization.

Prime pairs. The Hardy–Littlewood conjecture [6] predicts the density of prime pairs $(p, p+d)$ for fixed even d . Zhang [7] proved infinitely many pairs with gap $\leq 7 \times 10^7$; Maynard [8] reduced this to 246. These results confirm abundance but do not give density for the product form.

Novelty. OEIS A001358 (semiprimes) [14] and A072000 ($\pi_2(n)$) [15] address unconstrained semiprimes. A213025 (“balanced semiprimes”) [16] uses an unrelated definition (arithmetic mean of semiprime neighbors). No sequence for $B_D(x)$ or the gap-bounded variant was found. Project Euler problems 187 and 501 address semiprime counting [17] but without gap constraints.

7 Future Work

1. **Wheel-30 sieve.** Packing 8 bits per 30 numbers (vs. 1 bit per 2 numbers) halves the sieve array and POPCNT passes. `primesieve` [10] achieves 1.375 instructions per composite marking via a 64-position Duff’s device. Expected gain: $\sim 2\times$ on the sieve phase.
2. **Extended pre-sieve.** Covering primes up to 163 via 16 decomposed SIMD tables (~ 123 KB) could yield up to 30% additional speedup [10].
3. **Bucket sieve.** For $k > 10^{10}$, where the sieve range exceeds 2^{32} , the bucket sieve technique [13] would eliminate wasted iteration over large primes with no composites in the current segment.
4. **Formal lower bound.** Our impossibility result (Theorem 2) is structural. A formal $\Omega(\sqrt{x})$ lower bound in an appropriate computational model remains open.
5. **OEIS submission.** The sequence $B_D(x)$ for standard values of D could be submitted to OEIS as a new entry.

8 Conclusion

We introduced the gap-bounded semiprime counting problem, proved its asymptotic density $B_D(x) \sim D \int_2^{\sqrt{x}} dt / \ln^2 t$, argued that no sublinear algorithm can compute it, and presented a practical solver achieving $\sim 100\times$ speedup over a naïve baseline. The problem appears to be

novel and the algorithm reaches $k = 10^{10}$ in under 400 ms. The primary remaining optimization (wheel-30 sieve) is well-understood from the `primesieve` literature and expected to yield an additional $2\times$.

References

- [1] D. H. Lehmer, “On the exact number of primes less than a given limit,” *Illinois J. Math.*, 3:381–388, 1959.
- [2] J. C. Lagarias, V. S. Miller, A. M. Odlyzko, “Computing $\pi(x)$: The Meissel–Lehmer method,” *Math. Comp.*, 44(170):537–560, 1985.
- [3] Lucy_Hedgehog, “Efficient prime summation algorithm,” Project Euler Forums, 2013.
- [4] G. Broxey, “Lucy’s Algorithm + Fenwick Trees,” <https://gbroxey.github.io/blog/2023/04/09/lucy-fenwick.html>, 2023.
- [5] D. C. Crisan, R. Erban, “On the counting function of semiprimes,” *Integers*, 22:A49, 2022. arXiv:2006.16491.
- [6] G. H. Hardy, J. E. Littlewood, “Some problems of ‘Partitio Numerorum’; III,” *Acta Math.*, 44:1–70, 1923.
- [7] Y. Zhang, “Bounded gaps between primes,” *Ann. Math.*, 179(3):1121–1174, 2014.
- [8] J. Maynard, “Small gaps between primes,” *Ann. Math.*, 181(1):383–413, 2015.
- [9] D. Hirsch, I. Kessler, U. Mendlovic, “Computing $\pi(N)$: An elementary approach in $\tilde{O}(\sqrt{N})$ time,” *Math. Comp.*, 94(356), 2025. arXiv:2212.09857.
- [10] K. Walisch, `primesieve`: Fast prime number generator, <https://github.com/kimwalisch/primesieve>.
- [11] K. Walisch, `primecount`: Fast prime counting function, <https://github.com/kimwalisch/primecount>.
- [12] M. Deléglise, J. Rivat, “Computing $\pi(x)$: The Meissel, Lehmer, Lagarias, Miller, Odlyzko method,” *Math. Comp.*, 65(213):235–245, 1996.
- [13] T. Oliveira e Silva, “Fast implementation of the segmented sieve of Eratosthenes,” http://www.ieeta.pt/~tos/software/prime_sieve.html, 2002.
- [14] OEIS Foundation, “A001358: Semiprimes,” <https://oeis.org/A001358>.
- [15] OEIS Foundation, “A072000: Number of semiprimes $\leq n$,” <https://oeis.org/A072000>.
- [16] OEIS Foundation, “A213025: Balanced semiprimes of order 1,” <https://oeis.org/A213025>.
- [17] S. Brumme, “Project Euler 187: Semiprimes,” <https://euler.stephan-brumme.com/187/>.